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The Role and Significance of Robotics in Future Teachers of Technology

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Abstract: *In this article, the main aspects, role and importance of introduction of robotization systems as a subject to the future teachers of technology science, which are becoming the demand of today, were highlighted.*

Keywords: *Robotics, technology, artificial intelligence, programming, mechatronics, STEM.*

The role and importance of robotics for future technology teachers is extremely high, because robotics is one of the important directions in the development of modern science and technology. Through this subject, teachers will not only acquire technological knowledge, but will also have the opportunity to enrich the future generation with new knowledge. Below we consider the role and importance of robotics for future technology teachers:

1. Improvement of technological knowledge and skills

- Robotics is an integrated science of modern technologies, artificial intelligence, programming, mechatronics and mechanical engineering. This course allows teachers to master a lot of technical knowledge.
- Future teachers can learn engineering approaches through this subject and offer new innovative solutions to technological problems.

2. *Development of scientific and technical thinking*

- The science of robotics encourages teachers to think scientifically and technically. This will greatly help them in conveying the fundamentals of technical thinking to students in the course of the lesson. They teach how to approach engineering problems creatively, analyze and find solutions.

- Teachers should constantly familiarize themselves with technological innovations, which will increase their level of thinking and knowledge.

3. *Integration in STEM education*

- Robotics is an important part of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) education. In this field, teachers will have the opportunity to teach several subjects in an integrated manner, which will help students learn more and more deeply about scientific knowledge.
- Future teachers can develop multifaceted approaches and skills in students through robotics, such as mathematical analysis, physical processes, programming, and fundamentals of mechanics.

4. *Development of practical skills*

- In the practical part of robotics, teachers will have the opportunity to form important skills. For example, robots develop practical skills through tasks such as assembly, programming, control, and testing.
- These skills will allow teachers to organize their lessons more effectively and interactively in the future. Students understand real-life technological processes by working on robots in classes.

5. *Preparation for future professions*

- Robotics prepares future technology teachers for future professions. In modern society, many professions are related to automation and robotics. Therefore, teachers impart this knowledge to their students and form them as competitive specialists in the future.
- This subject also encourages students to think innovatively and find new solutions in the field of technology.

6. *Creation and engineering approach*

- Through robotics, teachers learn more about the engineering approach and develop their creativity by teaching this approach to students. Students learn to solve engineering problems by creating various projects in class.
- The teacher helps students to solve problems, develop projects and apply technical approaches, which is important for the formation of their creative and engineering skills.

The science of robotics, along with teaching future technology teachers deep technical knowledge and practical skills, plays an important role in the development of their scientific and technical thinking, and in the formation of innovative and creative thinking in students. This science, especially in the era of technological development, is of key importance in supporting STEM education and training future specialists.

The role and importance of robotics science in the future technology science teachers is important in the educational process. Robotics is inextricably linked with modern technology, computer science, programming, and mechanics, allowing teachers and students to develop innovative thinking and problem-solving skills. Below we consider the role and importance of robotics for future technology teachers:

1. Increasing technological knowledge:

- Robotics is necessary for technology teachers to have a deep understanding of modern technologies. This science combines mechanics, electronics, programming and artificial

intelligence and is used in various fields. By acquiring this knowledge, teachers can give new knowledge to students.

2. *Problem solving and creative approach:*

- Robotics develops problem solving, project management and technical creativity skills in teachers. In order to prepare students for future technological innovations, it is important for teachers to have solid knowledge in this area.
- Teaching interactive methods of solving real-life technical and mechanical problems through robotics develops students' technological creativity.

3. *As an important subject in STEM education:*

- Robotics is one of the main components in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education. Through this subject, teachers can use effective methods to teach students technical knowledge and skills.
- Through robotics, students will be able to practice physical laws, mathematics and informatics, and apply them in practice. This serves to enrich knowledge in the STEM field.

4. *Preparation for future professions:*

- Future technology teachers play an important role in preparing students for future professions through robotics. Robotics is important in many fields such as industry, medicine, agriculture, automation.
- Through this subject, teachers teach students advanced technologies and direct them to fields that are in demand in the labor market.

5. *Development of practical and experimental education:*

- Robotics teaching process helps to develop practical and experimental education. Teachers combine theoretical knowledge with practice by creating, programming and testing a robot together with students.
- This approach allows students to strengthen technical knowledge in practice, to study technological processes in the real world.

6. *An integral part of technological development:*

- Robotics is an integral part of future technological development. For future teachers, this subject creates a foundation for the implementation of new technological ideas and innovations. Robotics is important in teaching areas such as programming, automation, and artificial intelligence within the field of technology.

Robotics is a relevant and cutting-edge technology-related subject for future technology teachers, providing teachers with innovative approaches and advanced skills. This subject plays a key role in teaching future technologies, developing students' creative and problem-solving skills, and preparing them for modern technological fields.

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